

Original Research

Microfinance Institutions' Performance in Tanzania: Social Media Marketing Strategy Perspective

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Abstract

This research investigated the performance of microfinance institutions (MFIs) with the focus of social media marketing as the predictor of the performance. The research was carried out in Dodoma City whereas a cross-sectional research design with involvement of 84 staff selected proportionately from MFIs' strata was employed. Key informants were managers of the MFIs who were purposively selected. Data were collected using questionnaire and interviews. Analysis of qualitative data was undertaken by using adopting content analysis. Regarding quantitative data, application of descriptive statistics in form of percent, frequency and cases of occurrence in multiple responses fashion was carried out that was followed by further econometric analysis using and logit model to determine the performance of MFIs as contributed by social media as marketing strategies. The results indicated that WhatsApp, Instagram, Twitter and Facebook statistically were significant ($p < 0.05$) with positive relationship with increase in sales. The conclusion made from this research is that social media as marketing strategies positively influence the performance of MFIs. Serious investment in the usage of social media in marketing MFIs and their activities should be maximized for optimal performance.

Keywords: Microfinance institutions, performance, social media, social media marketing, Tanzania.

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Introduction

Globally, before the end of 1990's, television, radio and newspapers were the only established and known media applicable in supporting businesses (Kapoor *et al.*, 2018). As days went on, at the beginning of 2000s, the world underwent media revolution whereas introduction to social media was pronounced. Similar to other types of media, social media is a communication tool with wide range of social application and interaction which embraces usage of maximized accessibility and scalability techniques of communication (Singh and Sinha, 2017). Recently, a number of business institutions have adopted usage of social media integrating together marketing mix elements such as advertising, public relations and publicity, personal selling and sales promotion for the purpose of creating customer centered messages. The study of Lestari *et al.* (2024) in Indonesia reported that firms that have employed social media usage have improved performance of annual sales in the range of 10% to 30%, meaning that social media marketing is a crucial marketing strategy for firms' performance and growth. In China, Wu (2023) established that marketing through social media has enabled firms to attain high brand awareness, increased growth in sales and increased engagement of customers. As a result, such firms acquire strengths in competitiveness and consequently become market leaders. The study of Semenda *et al.* (2024) on the analysis of social media marketing strategies in Ukraine came up with results informing that as users of social media provide comments, likes and sharing of information the sales of the firm was being uplifted, signifying that social marketing strategy was important for enterprise growth. The evidence is drawn from several existing businesses that use social media such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Instagram and others is important (Kapoor *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, social media is concerned with vigorous usage of social media platforms as a promotional tool for products. Social media as a marketing tool has created business opportunities to MFIs to interact with a number of customers, sending out messages and receiving quick feedback at fairly minimal costs. In this study, social media is referred to as the use of WhatsApp, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn and Myspace so as to gain and disseminate business information to various stakeholders.

To connect with the global usage of social media marketing in African context, Lilembalemba and Phiri (2024) in Zambia came up with argument that social media marketing was statistically instrument in improving brand awareness in education sector. This implies that social media marketing when seriously integrated in business sector play a great role in communicating firm's services and products, leading to market penetration and increased market share. In a similar interpretation, Ramnarain *et al.* (2024) in KwaZulu Natal in South Africa informed that information shared through social commerce like Facebook build strong customer trust that consequently influence customer purchase decisions. This means that social commerce, if applied as marketing strategies, it is a powerful influencer to customers to quickly develop purchase decisions.

In Tanzania, microfinance institutions (MFIs) refer to organizations that provide financial services to the low- income earners, particularly micro enterprises (BOT, 2019). MFIs are largely concerned with provision of loans to needy members, issuance of insurance, financial deposits and other financial services (BOT, 2019). MFI as organizations provide microfinance services that are both regulated or unregulated that

include social intermediation services like formation of groups and intermediation of financial services including payments, credits, savings and insurance. MFIs operate as non-governmental organizations (NGOs), commercial banks, credit cooperatives, savings and credits. In this study, micro finance institutions are referred to as institutions availing financial services to low-income earners, particularly micro enterprises in Dodoma city. The establishment of microfinance is traced together with SACCOS (Savings and Credits Cooperative Societies) and NGOs back in 1995 whereas microfinance has continued growing internationally with remarkable achievement (Tanzanian Microfinance Institutions Directory, 2005). In 2005, Tanzania had 1,899 microfinance institutions (MFIs) compared to 665 MFIs as stated in the 2002 and this was due to expansion in coverage and entry of new MFIs (Tanzanian Microfinance Institutions Directory, 2005).

The study of Radobida (2019) expressed that financial inclusion provided by microfinance has grown to cover approximately half of the population of Tanzania and about 48.6% of the population received financial services from MFIs and financial NGOs in 2017. These findings expressed that about 50% of the population of Tanzania received financial services from less formalized financial institutions including Savings and Credit Associations (SACAs), Rotating Credit and Savings Associations (ROSCAs) and SACCOs and other types of MFIs. In this regard, it is evident that the microfinance sector has been servicing a great proportion of the population that would have been denied accessibility of financial services from highly formalized financial institutions (Financial Sector Deepening Trust, 2017). The evolution of microfinance was a strategy for economic development geared to provide benefits to Tanzanians with low-income, to date, the mission through their contributions has become evident. Though documentation of the impact of microfinance on societal wellbeing and economic growth has not been much detailed, still there is much to be recognized. For instance, a new financial culture has been initiated particularly in savings and loans uptake, deviating from the existing negative stigma that surrounded the previous lending practices (Kesanta and Andre, 2015; Mtamakaya *et al.*, 2018).

On the other hand, MFIs have faced several challenges such as increased number of bad debtors, unsatisfactory rate of loan repayments and diminishing of the capital owned by MFIs. The presence of other providers of financial services has subjected MFIs in a dilemma, hence, the rate of growth of MFIs has been in a questionable status provided that a good number of borrowers have been searching for financial services from other money lenders, posing a situation of failure for MFIs borrowers to promptly make repayment due to multiple loans (Mrisho, 2015).

To address the mentioned challenges confronting MFIs, the government of Tanzania has taken some initiatives. For instance, the National Microfinance Policy of 2000 (NMP, 2000) was formulated though it was unsuccessfully implemented, resulting from revision of the policy in 2017. For full operationalization of the 2017 NMP was fueled by the 2018 Microfinance Act that aimed at creating suitable environment for the microfinance sector in contributing to alleviation of poverty. The act also aimed at putting clarification for the already existing framework under which microfinance institutions were operated, regulated and governed, hence, addressing several encountered challenges (Tanzania Ministry of Finance and Planning, 2017) as adopted by Rabodiba (2019). To strengthen government support to MFIs, in 2009 the Tanzanian government established the

Electronic Government Agency (e-government or abbreviated eGa) in which in 2012 it was officially launched (Mandari and Koloseni, 2016). Furthermore, in 2017 regulations overseeing operations of social media and blogs known as the electronic and postal communications (Online Content) were signed by the Tanzanian government and they were published by the Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority (TCRA) whereas on March 2018 they were affected into use (Tobor, 2018).

Despite such efforts and initiatives taken by the government, and contributions of social media to different sectors and institutions, MFI still face problems such as high rate of bad debtors, unsatisfactory repayment of loans and diminishing of MFIs' capital just to mention a few. The linkage between micro finance institutions performance and social media is also not well established, despite increase in social media users in Tanzania but mainly they are users in social issues and small proportion of users in business issues including microfinance institution.

Generally, Kemp (2024) reported that in 2024 the population of Tanzanians actively connected to cellular phones is 67.72% which is equivalent to 99.0% of the total population. The population of Tanzanians connected with cellular phones has increased in 2024 as compared to that of 2023 which was 57.42% people equivalent to equivalent to 86.4% of a total population (Kemp, 2023). Kemp (2024) also informed that users of internet increase to 31.82 million people, equivalent to 39.9% as compared to 21 million internet users, equivalent to 31.6% (Kemp, 2023). In view of social media users, there has been an increase of users from 4.9 million equivalent to 7.4% of total population to 5.65 million users equivalent to 8.3% in 2024 (Kemp, 2024). Such proportion increase in social media usage in Tanzania calls up on for investigation on the extent of its usage in business perspective as the marketing strategy. As connected by Statcounter (2024), categorically, the usage of social media in a period of one year (June 2023 – 2024) was Facebook (36.04%), You Tube (17.22%), Pinterest (16.74%), Instagram (14.07%), Twitter (13.77%) and Reddit (0.94%) whereas Facebook being the most widely used social media. Empirically, usage of social media in Tanzania has been reported in various perspective including in social and economic perspectives.

The study of Ponera and Madila (2023) assessing usage of social media in Tanzania higher education students found that WhatsApp was the second widely used social media counting for 71.3% whereas education (classmates) being the first with 76% though it was suitable for academic purposes. Other commonly used social media were ResearchGate (60.2%), You Tube (49.1%), Shelfari for academic purposes (33.3%), Facebook (32.2%), Twitter (32.2%), LinkedIn (27.5%) and Myspace (8.2%). These results suggest that in Tanzanian higher education social media have been adopted by students in information sharing and communication. On the other side of a coin, Mhina (2023) made an examination of usage of social media in Tanzanian government employees, the results exposed that 21.4% of employees used WhatsApp that was followed by Facebook (16.5%), You Tube 14.2%, Instagram (12.4%), Twitter (7.6%). Google Plus (6.9%), Blogs (6.2%), Skype (6.2%) and WeChat (1.2%). The results further informed that only 5.2% of employees used social media in other uses including business while 94.9% used social media in social issues such as information sharing with peers, personal networking, entertainment and giving contributions to blogs of other people. Magolanga *et al.* (2022) carried out an examination of online social media usage by

journalists in provision of news regarding national development, the results implied that its usage in the field of news to report intended development projects is at infant stage.

The study was guided by the research questions: To what extent does social media as a marketing strategy influence MFIs' performance? What are challenges facing microfinance institutions when using social media marketing strategy? Understanding the influence of social media as a marketing strategy on microfinance institutions' performance will help to inform policy makers and management of microfinance institutions on extent of social media usage as a marketing strategy among microfinance institutions and its subsequent influence on the sales improvement as the measure of performance of micro finance institutions.

Theoretical Framework

This study was performed under the guidance of the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory which was founded by Wernerfelt (1984). RBV theory holds that the competitiveness of company is possibly achieved through delivering innovative superior customer value in a way customers feel satisfied. According to RBV theory, a firm operates well with accumulation of resources. The RBV advocates that the firm with unique resources is able to win and maintain competitive advantage. RBV theorists such as Barney (1986a; 1986b; 1991; 2001) insisted that sustainability of competitive advantage is justified by attaining and effective usage of a package of resources that can hardly be imitated and copied by competitors in the market. Such valuable resources are characterized by four features; they are valuable, rare, difficult to imitate and lack substitutes. Barney further defined such fundamental resources to involve firm's attributes, processes, assets, capabilities, knowledge and information that are under the control of the firm and from which strategies are formulated and implemented effectively and efficiently.

In this view, RBV theory proposes that resources that are rare, valuable, rare, hard to copy and lack substitutability best place a firm for long-run success. This theory has been applicable in several recent studies that worked on the application of the RBV theory in terms of value addition made by the resource to the firm. For instance, Mashenene and Kumburu (2020) investigated the value created to the firm by employees with various features such as honesty, commitment and competence, the findings revealed that such employees' features statistical theory holds the determination and ownership of important resources that contains vital features created valuable contribution to the firms' performance. In a similar way, Salazar and Armando (2017) studied the component of value creation as one of important assets or resource in RBV. Kazungu (2023) also used RBV theory to study the influence of network linkages as valuable resource on the performance of SMEs in handcraft industry in Tanzania. The findings revealed that competitiveness of the firm is embedded in the value created by the resources in use. These previous studies collectively suggest that firms' that use resources that create value are likely to be competitive and remain at the competitive edge.

In this regard, this theory was applicable in this study since technology was considered as the strategic resource that create value to the firms. In the focus of this study, technological resource in form of social media comprising of Facebook, WhatsApp,

Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn and Myspace was considered to have value creation to the firm and formed the independent variables. In this view, social media are used by microfinance to market and communicate their products and programmes with customers at a wide reach with low cost. In this case, microfinance firms acquire competitive advantage through usage of social media as a differentiation strategy, consequently, enabling such firms to enjoy market leadership strategy through market penetration and attaining of large market share. Connectedly, usage of social media by microfinance firms become a focus strategy from which such firms have the chance to focus their communications on specific market segments based on various characteristics such as age, sex, income, shopping preferences, pattern, behaviour and usage. Such focus strategy enables microfinance firms to utilize profitably available resources with the aim of maximizing service targeting and positioning, meaning that, the performance of the firms is easily improved.

Empirical Literature Review

The term social media entails interactive technologies which that computer-mediated that help to create and share ideas, information, career interests and other types of expression through virtual networks and communities (Jan and Hermkens, 2011; Jonathan and Steve, 2015). Focusing on the current study, social media included social sites for networking such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram and MySpace and business/professional networking sites such as LinkedIn. Social media marketing refers to a kind of online marketing with requirement to create and share content on social media networks with the purpose of achieving branding and marketing objectives. Social media marketing focuses on activities that require to post texts and updating videos, images and other contents that necessitate engagement with audience and usage of paid social media advertising (Candace Consulting, 2019).

Microfinance institutions are money lenders and bankers which offer microfinance services including insurance, loans, deposits, fund transfer and payment. Microfinance institutions always provide highly required financial services to entrepreneurs, households and emerging businesses which would have been denied access to such services in the absence of microfinance institutions (Teeboom, 2019). Singh (2022) in India pointed out that the significance of social media to microfinance institutions included improvement of insights for customers, services for customers, cost efficient and connectivity with the purpose of improving sales and create brand awareness. Recently, several studies focusing on the influence of social media usage on organizational performance and growth of different organizations, financial institutions and companies have been carried out globally and are receiving increased attention over the years. For instance, Dodokh (2017) in Jordan employing quantitative research approach investigated the impact of usage of social media on firms' performance in dead sea products. The findings showed the impact was positive and statistically significant on firms' performance in term of reduction of costs, time to market, quick adaptation, innovation and satisfaction.

In Africa, Mahboub (2018) assessed the relationship between usage of social media and performance in banking sector in North Africa and Middle East using quantitative research approach, the findings demonstrated positive and significant relationship in

terms of profitability, growth and environmental performance. Emeka *et al.* (2015) in Nigeria investigated the chosen platforms of social media and their usefulness in promoting tourism, the study exposed that social media platforms were effective in promoting tourism development and such contribution was statistically significant. Okari (2017) in Kenya established the relationship between financial performance and usage of social media among microfinance institutions. The findings presented that usage of social media particularly Facebook was adopted by microfinance institutions, and it had positive contribution on the performance of businesses through intensified interaction between institutions and customers. The findings further showed that social media provided sales and marketing platforms for products, accessibility to customers' comments, needs and real time feedback for the improved customer satisfaction. Moreover, the findings indicated that an average of 50% of new customers were acquired by means of social media usage leading to an average of 50% increase of loan portfolio for the past three years of microfinance institutions' operations. This is remarkable growth emanated from social media which need to be embraced, prioritized and integrated in business operations.

Kazungu *et al.* (2017) worked on the relationship between social media and the performance of micro enterprises in Tanzania by focusing on increase in sales, profit, customer base and brand improvement. The results denoted that micro enterprises have been using social media to the large extent that has led to attract a number of new customers and satisfying needs of existing customers with improved brand image, brand awareness, customer base, profit and sales. The study of Lweno and Mashenene (2021) focused on online marketing strategies in creating customer loyalty in Tanzania using both quantitative and qualitative research approach, the findings denoted that online marketing strategies statistically were significant, suggesting that companies should focus on the usage of social media. Another study by Mashenene and Lambileki (2022) on perceived quality of e-banking services using NMB Bank as case of study, the findings expressed that e-banking services were positively perceived by NMB customers. As pointed earlier, some studies on social media usage focused on education, Masele and Rwehikiza (2022) in Tanzania came out with findings that usage of traditional media was predominantly used compared to social media platforms in higher education. The findings further informed that for the occasions where social media platforms were adopted, they have become effective means of information sharing, feedback giving, enhancing institution's visibility and broadened information reach.

Following the reviewed literature, a summary of a research gap is hereby drawn in various ways on usage of social media as a marketing tool in determining performance of MFIs in Tanzania. A gap is drawn from a number of previous studies being inclined towards usage of social media in social and education perspective, leaving unattended mainly business perspective. The statistics presented in previous studies magnify the gap and pose a dilemma as in one hand they indicate increase in social media users in Tanzania but mainly in social and education perspectives while posing meagre usage of social media in business perspective. Furthermore, a few studies that dealt with usage of social media in business perspective have mainly focused on other types of businesses other than microfinance institutions and their performance emanating from usage of social media. Another area connected to a gap to be filled is that mainly previous studies were undertaken in other regions other than Dodoma region particularly Dodoma city, the city whose population and business activities are growing at an exponential rate following the

transfer of capital city from Dar es Salaam to Dodoma in 2016 (URT, 2022; Mlay, 2017), the decision that has fueled mushrooming of businesses that consequently require financial institutions including microfinance for finance them. The URT (2022) indicated that the population of Dodoma increased from 2,083,588 in 2012 (NBS, 2013) to 3,085,625 (URT, 2022), the increase of approximately 48.09% which is substantial to support increase in business activities. Therefore, the present study was performed to cover the gap by determining how social media as marketing strategy influence the performance of micro finance institutions in Dodoma city.

Research Methods

Research design

The current research was undertaken by adopting descriptive cross-sectional survey research design so as to describe variables of interest under the research. A descriptive research design was used since the researchers intended to investigate the influence of social media on the performance of micro finance. Studies adopting descriptive design always describe phenomena about what, who, when, where and how will be performed (McCombes, 2019). This design was opted given the fact that researchers were constrained with time and financial resources (Mashene, 2016).

Sampling

The research was carried out in Dodoma city for selected microfinance institutions, Dodoma city was purposefully selected following the argument that it is a city in Dodoma region where government operations have been shifted from Dar es Salaam to Dodoma in 2016. Following this government decision to shift from Dar es Salaam to Dodoma, Dodoma city has been experienced as the fastest growing city in Tanzania, as the result, the city has become a favourable ground for several mushrooming business entities which call for financial services. Mlay *et al.* (2017) established existence of viable business and investment opportunities in Dodoma region resulting from exponential increase in population. This shift of government operations from Dar es Salaam has resulted in an increase in population in Dodoma region from 2,083,588 (URT, 2012) to 3,085,625 (URT, 2022), making an increase in population size of 1,002,037 people which is equivalent to 48.09% increase in a period of 10 years from 2012 to 2022.

During the time of study, Dodoma city had a total of 42 active microfinance institutions that were categorized into microfinance banks, NGOs and micro credit companies with a total number of 1,000 employees (TAMFI, 2019). The consideration for selection of microfinance institution for the study among other criteria was microfinance institutions that had been in operation for a period of five years since establishment, this criterion was aimed at enabling researchers to collect sufficient data with high robustness (Mashene, 2016). Also, the microfinance institutions which had only one employee been excluded from the study since in most cases such employees were busy throughout the time, hence, this necessitated for exclusion. Further, during the study some microfinance institutions were found to have temporarily suspended their operations were excluded from the study.

Based on the itemized criteria, 16 microfinance institutions were selected from 42 microfinance institutions. The selected institutions included Nuru Prime Business, Fanikiwa Microfinance Company Limited, Ibrahimu Microcredit Limited, Finca Microfinance Bank, Vision Fund Tanzania Microfinance Bank Limited, BRAC Tanzania Finance Limited, Centre for Community Initiative, Platinum Credit Ltd- Tanzania, Imarisha Maisha Limited, A.F.S Limited, Frolian Company Limited, Mwinami Micro Credit, Renamu Company Limited, Liciouslight Microfinance Limited, Boniface Microfinance Limited and Bewra Microfinance Company Limited. The useful population of the study from the selected microfinance institutions was 336 employees. The formula by Yamane (1967) as adopted by Rwegoshora (2006) was used in estimating the sample size (equation 1).

$$n = N / [1 + N (e)^2] \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Whereby:

n = Sample size

N = Total population

e = Level of precision/error of detection (10%)

1 = Constant

$$\text{Therefore } n = 336 / [1 + 336 (0.1)^2] = 77$$

From the calculation, the sample size was 77 staff from microfinance banks, NGOs, and micro credit companies in Dodoma city. However, during the field, there was an addition of seven (7) questionnaire that were administered making a total of sample size of 84. The additional sample size was found useful due to willingness and voluntary in nature of respondents that emerged during the field. All (100%) useful questionnaires were returned by staff of microfinance institutions. The decision to make use of additional sample size is common in several previous studies, for instance, Mashenene (2016) used a sample size of 254 instead of the already established sample size of 250. In a similar way, Tundui (2012) adopted a sample size of 310 instead of 300 that was predetermined.

Adoption of both proportionate stratified and purposive sampling techniques to select the sample was taken on board. Selecting 16 managers as key informants from the MFIs was carried out purposefully. The selection of these managers was due to the fact that such managers were believed to have a lot of valuable information regarding MFIs. On the other hand, the staff of MFIs existed in three strata that were categorized into microfinance banks, NGOs and micro credit companies. The strata were formed based on the staff having shared attributes or characteristics. With MFIs in Dodoma city having 336 employees, researchers selected 84 staff from the predetermined strata based on the category of MFIs belong to. A proportionate stratified sampling was involved in selecting staff from population in the respect stratum. This resulted in the selection of 18 staff from microfinance banks, 8 staff from NGOs, and 58 from micro credit companies. The

selected number of staff from each stratum were obtained by dividing the number of staff in each stratum by total population in all strata times the sample size (Table 1).

Table 1. Sample size estimation

Category Of Mfis	Number Of Staff In Strata	Proportionated Sample	Number Of Staff Selected
Microfinance Banks	72	$72/336 \times 84$	18
Ngos	32	$32/336 \times 84$	8
Micro Credit Companies	232	$232/336 \times 84$	58
Total	336		84

Data collection

Quantitative data collection

Survey method was used in collecting quantitative data whereas semi-structured questionnaire as a tool for collecting data was designed and administered from 1st April 2020 to 28th April 2020. The questionnaire was composed of questions with 5 points Likert scale (1=strongly disagree and 5=strongly agree), these questions were used to collect data on independent variables about social media; Facebook (three items), WhatsApp (three items), Twitter (three items), Instagram (three items), MySpace (three items) and LinkedIn (three items). Data for the dependent variable in form of performance of microfinance institutions was also collected using 5 points Likert scale (four items). The questionnaire also consisted of questions aiming at collecting respondents' demographic characteristics; age, sex, level of education and work experience.

Qualitative data collection

With the aim of supplementing quantitative data, qualitative data were collected using interview method whereas managers of microfinance institutions were exposed to interview using interview guide from 10th April 2020 to 15 April 2020. The interview sessions with managers lasted for an average of 32 minutes and the end point for the interviews was determined by saturation point that was reached where no new responses were solicited from managers. The interview focused on addressing questions including benefits accruing from usage of social media platforms, challenges encountered in terms of internet accessibility, internet cost, feedback from customers, awareness and insecurity concerns. During the interview sessions, responses were recorded using notebook and in some cases upon approval of requested consent by interviewees, smartphone was used as an electronic device to record data. To ensure reliability of data collected from interview was enhanced, thorough documentation, detailed and comprehensive descriptions and debriefing by peers were keenly observed (Ahmed, 2024).

Data analysis

Qualitative data analysis

Data obtained through structured interviews were qualitatively subjected to content analysis whereas examination, categorization, tabulation and recombination of evidence were performed with the aim of addressing the problem under study (Yin, 2014). Content analysis comprised of various steps whereas collected data underwent preparatory stage that was followed by familiarization stage. As in procedures of content analysis, coding at initial stage was performed that was followed by developing categories, data refining and finally selection of codes. Themes and patterns were further analyzed in which identification of new themes was performed and patterns and relationships were recognized thereafter. The final step involved interpreting, reporting of findings, extracting meaning from codes, contextualizing with themes and carrying out of effective communication of findings. During the analysis, researchers worked hard in understanding respondents' views from interview sessions and made interpretations thereafter (Mashenene, 2016). Further, the findings from the study were comparatively matched with those from the literature and empirical evidence elsewhere (Mashenene and Kumburu, 2020; Maziku and Mashenene, 2020; Mashenene, 2019).

Quantitative data analysis and analytical model

Before analyzing quantitative data, editing and validation of data to sort out useful from non-useful. The useful data thereafter were subjected into data analysis whereas they were coded and later entered into the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) and cleaned. After data entry and cleaning, descriptive analysis was performed as one of quantitative data analysis method whereas frequency, percent, mean and standard deviations were computed. Determination of the influence of social media as marketing strategy on the microfinance institutions' performance was undertaken using an econometric model called binary logistic regression (logit) based on the fact that performance of microfinance as dependent variable was categorized into dummy variable (1, 0). The equation for logit model was as follows (equation 2):

$$\Pr(Y=1/x) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Fb + \beta_2 Wh + \beta_3 Tw + \beta_4 In + \beta_5 Ms + \beta_6 Ln + \epsilon_i \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Whereby:

Y = Performance of microfinance institutions

Fb = Facebook

Wh = WhatsApp

Tw = Twitter

In = Instagram

Ms = MySpace

Ln = LinkedIn

β = Coefficient of change

ε = Error term

Findings and Discussion

Reliability Test

Table 2 summarizes the coefficients for Cronbach's alpha reliability test. The findings indicate that the coefficients for Cronbach's alpha fallen in a range between 0.789 and 0.996, indicating a high level of reliability. The results show that all variables met the Cronbach Alpha coefficient of above 0.7 as suggested by Pallant (2016) and DeVellis (2012) and were therefore considered for subsequent further analysis. The study of Mashene and Kumburu (2020) was revealed to have high level of reliability since it established Cronbach's alpha coefficients with the range between 0.782 and 0.909. Therefore, the internal consistency was thoughtful sufficiently high and adequately measured the variables of the study.

Table 2. Test for reliability

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha (α)	Number of items
Facebook	0.990	3
WhatsApp	0.960	3
Twitter	0.993	3
Instagram	0.982	3
MySpace	0.996	3
LinkedIn	0.984	3
Performance	0.789	4

Sample Characteristics

Sex

Table 3 shows that the majority (57.1%) of respondents was female and 42.9% were male. The findings imply that female employees to the larger extent overrepresented their counterpart male in microfinance institutions. These findings were consistent to those of Madden and Zickuhr (2012) which established that female were users of internet and social networks with higher proportion compared to male. In a similar way Hampton *et al.* (2011) revealed that female as users of social networking site had more representation with 56% domination over male their counterpart.

Table 3. Sample Characteristics (n=84)

Variables	Frequency	Percents
Sex		
Male	36	42.9
Female	48	57.1
Total	84	100.0
Age category (Years)		

Variables	Frequency	Percents
Less 20	2	2.4
20- 39	82	97.6
Total	84	100.0
Level of education		
Secondary education	4	4.8
Diploma	31	36.9
Degree	46	54.8
Postgraduate	3	3.6
Total	84	100.0
Working experience		
1-3	35	41.7
4-6	43	51.2
7 years and above	6	7.1
Total	84	100.0

Age

Table 3 indicates that 97.6% of all respondents were aged between 20 and 39 years while only 2.4% of respondents were below 20 years old. This shows that majority of the staff working in microfinance institutions belonged to the productive (economic) age group. Therefore, the findings indicate the majority of age group using social media marketing strategies activities was youth. These findings are in line with those of Novelli (2017) which established that youth form the majority of ICT users in Tanzania.

Education level

Table 3 shows that 54.8% of respondents had bachelor degree education compared to 36.9%, 4.8% and 3.6% with diploma, secondary and postgraduate education respectively. The results evince that accumulatively 95.3% of respondents had Diploma education and above. These findings agree with those of Kulanga (2018) which revealed that large proportion of selected SMEs in Dodoma had college education, therefore, they had necessary skills to use social media marketing strategies to carry out business operations in different aspects of administration, IT, finance and legal.

Working experience

The results in Table 3 specify that 51.2% of the respondents have worked in the corresponding microfinance institutions in their current positions for 4-6 years followed by 41.7% working for 1-3 years and only 7.1% working above 7 years. These findings mean that respondents had sound working experience in their current positions, hence, they were familiar microfinance operations. Therefore, based on wide range of experience, such staff are most likely to engage themselves in usage of social media tools as marketing strategies. These results were reinforced with those of Mirza *et al.* (2009) which established that bank staff with the age ranging between three and 16 years of experience were on position to adopt new technologies like internet banking and social media marketing.

Descriptive Statistics Results

Social media sites used in microfinance institutions

Table 4 illustrates that Facebook accounted to 97.6% cases followed by Instagram with 94.0% of the cases. Further, WhatsApp and Twitter had 85.7% and 75.0% cases of occurrence respectively. Therefore, these findings imply that Facebook, WhatsApp and Instagram are the main social media marketing strategies used by microfinance in Dodoma city. These findings coincide with those of Hanna *et al.* (2017) which suggested that Facebook, Instagram and WhatsApp have replaced the traditional way of undertaking marketing and communication by shifting to internet-based marketing and communication which is more influential. The findings also reach agreement with those in Brown (2016) which expressed that 67 percent and 51 used WhatsApp and Facebook respectively to buy products that were forwarded on companies' social media sites. In a similar way, the results are reinforced by those of Radhika *et al.* (2023) which established that social media is an important marketing strategy which the effect on relationship marketing. The qualitative results further strengthened quantitative results through the following exhibition:

“...Yes, we do, and we mainly use Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and WhatsApp as marketing communication strategies/tools. Our sales have been improving from time to time since we started seriously adopting social media marketing initiatives, and for sure it lowers marketing costs ...”
 (Interview conducted with BRAC Manager on 13th April 2020).

Table 4. Social media sites used (n=84)

Social media	Responses		Percent of Cases
	N	Percent	
Facebook	82	22.2	97.6
Twitter	63	17.0	75.0
Instagram	79	21.4	94.0
WhatsApp	72	19.5	85.7
Myspace	42	11.5	50.0
LinkedIn	31	8.4	36.9
Total	369	100.0	439.2

Empirical Results

Tests for logit model

Testing of logit model was carried out whereas findings in Table 5 indicate that binary logistic regression model fitted well in the data as measured by Pseudo- R^2 (Cox and Snell R square = 0.507 and Nagelkerke R square = 0.680), indicating that independent variables recorded into the logit model described 50.7% and 68.0% of variance in the dependent variable. The binary logistic regression model gives an acceptable fit if it indicates an improvement on the model without predictors (Field, 2013). Initially, the -2Log likelihood without variables was 82.623 and with all predictors had -2Log likelihood of

54.890. The decrease in the value of -2Log likelihood shows model improvement, hence, suggesting data fitness in the model was pronounced (Mashenene, 2016). Similarly, the model containing all predictors was significant at $P < 0.05$ with $\chi^2(6)$ of 58.7, informing that data fitness in the model was achieved. Further, Hosmer and Lemeshow test was performed to test model goodness of fit. The model containing all predictors gave a $\chi^2(6)$ of 4.217 which was insignificant ($p = 0.731$), implying that data fitness in the model.

Table 5: Logit results (n = 84)

Variables	B	S.E.	Sig.	Exp(B)
Facebook (index score)	3.409	0.854	0.000	30.222
Twitter (index score)	2.001	0.744	0.007	7.396
Instagram (index score)	1.730	0.770	0.024	9.176
WhatsApp (index score)	2.137	0.747	0.004	8.472
LinkedIn (index score)	-0.295	0.687	0.667	0.744
Myspace (index score)	0.732	0.699	0.295	2.080
Constant	-0.873	0.434	0.044	0.418
Omnibus Test (χ^2) = 58.7(6), $p = 0.02$ Hosmer and Lemeshow (χ^2) = 4.217 (6), $p = 0.731$ Number of observations = 84 Cox and Snell R square = 0.507 Nagelkerke R square = 0.680 -2 Log Likelihood = 54.890 Dependent variable (1 = If social media increased sales, 0 = Otherwise)				

Logit results

The findings in Table 5 revealed that Facebook had positive effect in increasing sales in microfinance institutions ($\beta = 3.409$) and statistically significant (p -value = 0.000). The findings exposed that 1 unit rise in Facebook followers will lead to sales increase in microfinance institutions by 340%. This also has been indicated by odds ratio of 30.22 which connote that the likelihood of Facebook as a social media to increase sales of microfinance is 30.2 times. These findings are in line with those of Paquette (2017) and Safko and Brake (2018) which explained that various discounts and promotions presented on business Facebook pages resulted into multiple increase in sales. The findings further are in line with the Resource Based Theory in a sense that investigated social media platforms formed a strategic technological resource, hence, contributing to the theory that social media platforms are strategic technological resource.

The findings in Table 5 exposed that Twitter positively affected sales increase in microfinance institutions ($\beta = 2.001$) and statistically significant (p -value = 0.007). The findings suggested that as one unit of Twitter followers increases, sales in microfinance institutions increase by 200%. This is evidently signified by odds ratio of 7.396 connoting that the likelihood of Twitter to increase performance in terms of sales in microfinance institutions is 7.4 times. These findings are in connection to those of Levinson and Gibson (2015) that established that twitter is the cost-effective marketing solution for businesses

elsewhere. Similarly, the study of Koroma (2016) contended that more than half of medium sized firms valued social media including twitter since it profited their businesses via enhanced sales volume.

The findings in Table 5 exposed that Instagram had a positive effect in growing sales in microfinance institutions ($\beta = 1.730$) and statistically significant ($p\text{-value} = 0.024$). The findings revealed that raising one unit of Instagram followers will uplift sales in microfinance institutions by 173%. Statistically, the odds ratio of 9.176 depicts that the likelihood of Instagram to increase performance of microfinance in terms of sales is 9.2 times. These findings were like those of Oyza and Edwin (2015) which clarified that dispatched information in social media such as Instagram is a supportive source and is expected to influence consumers' decision-making process. Moreover, the study informed that consumers make use of information on Instagram as the parameter for their upcoming purchase decisions that triggered sales growth. Additionally, Instagram is an advertising tool for marketers who make use of this advantage in creating marketing strategy which helps them to increase more customers and sales in return.

The findings in Table 5 showed that WhatsApp had positive effect in raising sales of microfinance institutions ($\beta = 2.137$) and statistically significant ($p\text{-value} = 0.004$). The findings exposed that raising one unit of WhatsApp followers will result in sales increase in microfinance institutions by 213.7%. These findings are also evidenced by odds ratio of 8.472 indicating that the likelihood of WhatsApp to increase performance of microfinance in terms of sales was 8.5 times. In view of these findings, a synergy with the Resource Based View Theory can be established with the connection that resources can be human, financial and technological. In this study, technology was a pivotal point. Technologically, social media as the resource which encompasses Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter and Instagram support the study findings as it is a useful the marketing strategy to increase sales in microfinance institutions.

Challenges facing microfinance institutions when using social media

The study found various challenges that encountered by microfinance institutions when using social media. Findings in Table 6 reveal that the critical challenges were high internet costs, internet accessibility, customer feedback, insecurity/cybercrime and inadequate awareness of social network platforms.

Table 6. Challenges facing microfinance institutions when using social media (n=84)

Challenges	Responses		Percent of Cases
	N	Percent	
High internet cost	82	21.8	95.3
Accessibility of internet	71	18.9	84.5
Feedback from customers	79	21.0	94.0
Insecurity (cybercrime)	80	21.3	95.2
Inadequate awareness of social network platforms	64	17.0	76.2
Total	376	100.0	445.2

High internet cost (Table 6) was the first challenge that encountered by micro finance institutions when using social media in Dodoma city with 95.3 % cases of occurrence. This informs that high costs accompanying adoption of social media marketing strategies was one of the key limitations for the microfinance institutions to realize desired goals. These findings show similarity with Njau and Karangu (2016) which found that large proportion of Kenyan firms are reluctant to adopt e-marketing due to high cost perceived in the development of electronic infrastructure. The qualitative results further strengthened quantitative results through the following exhibition:

“...Social media needs funds for internet cost and it needs human resources and time to interact with customers...” (Interview conducted with manager, Platinum Credit Ltd – Tanzania on 8th April 2020).

Insecurity (cybercrime) (Table 6) from the customers was a second challenges that encountered by micro finance institutions when using social media in Dodoma city with 95.2 % cases of occurrence. These findings are similar to these of Bostanshirin (2014) found that security in implementing virtual space in operation was one of critical challenges facing online marketing. The qualitative results further strengthened quantitative results through the following exhibition:

“...Cyber-crimes in social media like hacking of social media sites/platforms and Competitors may mislead your customers /followers using social media platforms and their platforms...” (Interview conducted with manager, Ibrahim Micro Credit Limited on 8th April 2020).

Feedback from the customers (Table 6) was a third challenges that encountered by micro finance institutions when using social media in Dodoma city with 94.0 % cases of occurrence. These findings are similar to these of Ndlobo and Dhurup (2017) in South Africa which expressed that customer feedback was one of the challenges in Microfinance Bank Limited. The qualitative results further strengthened quantitative results through the following exhibition:

“...Using social media may lead to get customers who were resistant to pay back loans, this is because they are not familiar with them, but you only met through social media...” (Interview conducted with manager, Liciouslight Microfinance Limited on 4th April 2020).

Accessibility of internet (Table 6) was a fourth challenges that encountered by micro finance institutions when using social media in Dodoma city with 84.5% cases of occurrence. These findings are similar to these of Kazungu *et al.* (2017) found that over 60% of the owners of SMEs owners supported that limited internet accessibility obstruct application of e-marketing strategies. The qualitative results further strengthened quantitative results through the following exhibition:

“...Challenges on using social media include: In remote areas social media is not common and sometimes no network coverage, Some Microfinance Institutions which are NGOs their policies are about not to use social media and Information may go to unintended people such as below 18 years....”

(Interview conducted with manager, Vision fund Tanzania on 9th April 2020).

Inadequate awareness of social network platforms (Table 6) was a fifth challenges that encountered by micro finance institutions when using social media in Dodoma city with 76.2 % cases of occurrence, informing that for users to strongly use social media, level of awareness creation should be intensified. These findings are in line with those Kanchanatanee *et al.* (2014) in Thailand which found existence of negative perception among social media users on usefulness of e-marketing in business. The qualitative results further strengthened quantitative results through the following exhibition:

“...Challenges on using social media include, some customers do not have smart phones. FINCA mostly concentrates on low-income earners who mostly do not own smartphones, Awareness is low to use smart phones for business activities like accessing information from FINCA and other MFIs and Network problems in local areas/ far away from town since FINCA also serves those who are away from town like Mkoha area...” (Interview conducted with FINCA Manager on 12th April 2020).

Conclusion

The study conclude that Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp and Twitter demonstrated positive relationship with increasing sales in microfinance institution and statistically significant. This implies that the studied social media marketing strategies positively influence microfinance institutions' performance through increase in sales. Therefore, Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp and Twitter are the social media platforms to be integrated in firms' marketing and communication plans for improved performance. This means that, careful market segmentation should be performed to identify profitable market segments, target and focus on them and carry out positioning using social medial platforms. The conclusion is further drawn that effective use of social media platforms help firms to acquire and maintain competitive advantage in terms of differentiation and cost leadership. Furthermore, the study found that high internet cost, insecurity (cybercrime) and feedback from the customers were pointed out as the major challenges encountered by microfinance institutions when using social media, this calls for effective strategies to curb such challenges. The findings from the study further provide basis for theoretical implication in which social media platforms should be viewed as integral component in the Resource Based Theory as technological resource which is used as a competitive advantage by firms.

Recommendations

The study recommends to the Telecommunication Regulatory Communication Authority (TCRA), the Ministry of Information, Communication and Information Technology and other IT stakeholders, to put into operations improved initiatives geared to strengthen internet connectivity and accessibility to the large community. This will motivate microfinance institutions to effectively use internet and social media in business operations. Further, TCRA and other IT stakeholders to collaboratively create awareness

to the public on the usefulness of social media marketing strategies if integrated in business operations.

The study also recommends that the microfinance institutions to aggressively opt for social media marketing strategies over the traditional ones. In this concern, prioritization on the usage of Facebook, Instagram and WhatsApp should seriously opted by microfinance institutions in order to achieve desired goal of improved performance. This recommendation comes from the truth that the statistics indicate that a lot of time is spent by customers on social media, hence, providing an opportunity for microfinance to exploit available markets profitably due to wide and quick reach to customers with minimum costs.

Limitations and areas for future research

The research was limited to Dodoma city with the focus to only one business sector, microfinance institutions. It is therefore recommended that similar research should be carried out across many cities in Tanzania to be able to establish the extent of social media usage across the cities. Further, many business sectors should be involved in further research to be able to carry out comparative analysis and recommend appropriate strategies to be taken across sectors.

Author Contributions

The first author was a master's degree student who developed research proposal, collected and analysed data and wrote the research report. The second author supervised the student throughout the research project, and he wrote the manuscript in consultation with the first author.

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